

Programmatic Text

(English translation from the original Russian manuscript)

Today we need Scriabin

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Scriabins, Scriabin-like sensations.

Scriabinization.

All that he dreamed of, having felt it almost a hundred years ago.

And having opened it. Or rather — having slightly opened it.

Opened it for himself, and slightly opened it for us.

He allowed himself exactly as much time as was needed to point the way.

For us — those who would step beyond the century.

Alas, his time, the time of the Silver Age,

illuminated his work with the bright glow of talent,

but did not provide the technical means.

Matter had not yet matured.

He simply outpaced it. And by far.

Such is the fate of technology —

to trail behind talent,

behind thought, innovation, invention.

And each time, with enviable regularity,

we humans repeat the same mistakes, mistakes, mistakes —

painful and crude.

At first Scriabin was worshipped:

by those who understood, and by those who merely echoed approval.

Then they rushed to decipher him.

But the wrong people deciphered him.

And they deciphered the wrong thing.

They began in the wrong place.

And ended in the wrong place.

And so it turned out as it did. A parody.

A technical experiment instead of the foresight of a genius.

One has to imagine it!

Scriabin — and blinking little lights, laser scanning.

And this — in our century,

synthetic by its very nature.

It is not Scriabin's colored hearing,

not Scriabin's luminous line that needs deciphering —

let us leave that to scholars and researchers! —

It is his synthetic ideas that must be embodied,

ideas to which, it seems, representatives of the creative professions have not yet matured.

And yet everything is so simple —

one only needs to flip the switch!..

Not on a device,

but in the mind!

And first of all — in the heart!
True, for this one must try to understand
why Scriabin was regarded with such genuine interest by
the poets Vyacheslav Ivanov, Konstantin Balmont, Jurgis Baltrušaitis,
Valery Bryusov, Alexander Blok;
by theatre directors Vsevolod Meyerhold, Alexander Tairov;
by gifted painters, writers.
But perhaps one of the most important names
in this not-so-long chain
is Hazrat Inayat Khan — philosopher and musician,
a leading representative of the spiritual tradition of Sufism.
Why did Inayat Khan and Alexander Scriabin
accept and feel one another so freely and unconditionally
after only five minutes of acquaintance,
which took place in 1914 in Moscow, at the home of Vyacheslav Ivanov?

SCRIABIN:

Such greatness and such calm.
This is precisely what has been lost
in our exhausted, limited life.

INAYAT KHAN:

I thought that if this idea were ever to be realized,

despite the difficulties arising at the beginning,
such music could become the music of the entire world.
Which, in turn, could contribute
to the unification of humanity into a universal brotherhood.

Art was necessary for the human being
and will always be necessary.

It is a shock.

Without which we cannot live.

Without which life becomes dull, colorless,
worth absolutely nothing.

Scriabin's art will give us this missing element,
will fill the Void,
will fill the Silence,
will make Light sound,
and through a new sensation will help create a New Art —
the art of the twenty-first century, of the next millennium.

Because to Scriabin's experience
the technology of today will be added.

The new art has matured.

We — our feelings — have also matured.

In certain scattered elements
this art is already visible.

True, most often in the form of a trick.

But a trick in art always demands
submission to a higher artistic purpose.

That purpose will be shock.

It is time for enormous hidden layers,
long dormant within us,
to come to the surface.

And to begin to interact:

Music, Light, dance,

and "the intoxicating aroma of wild flowers and grasses" —

everything beautiful that is hidden within us
and everything that surrounds us.

He left this world young in body,
at the full height of his powers,
having foretold the day of his death long in advance.

He clearly knew the boundary
where his mission would end.

He understood this at the very moment
when he fully realized
that what had been revealed had been revealed first to him,

that he had stepped beyond an entire century — or more —
simultaneously sensing doom and solitude.

His thought, his genius foresight,
at a certain level cast off the physical body itself
in order to give way
to a beautiful dream,
a flame-throwing explosion,
an endless flight,
a transformation into ether.

Only Ether.

It is Light.

It is Music.

It is Dance and Incense.

It is Everything and Nothing.

And in order to find oneself.

To regain oneself

a hundred years later — or a little later —

in

embodiment.

(Daniel A. Freedman, "Dedication to Alexander Nikolaevich Scriabin", 2000)